

Analyzing Pulse Position Modulation Time Hopping UWB in IEEE UWB Channel

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Abstract: Ultra-wideband (UWB) employs very narrow band pulses of nano-seconds duration to provide high data rate communications. Pulses spread the energy over a wide frequency because of that it is called ultra-wideband. Ultra wideband (UWB) technology, useful for both communication and sensing applications, uses the radio spectrum differently than the vast majority of radio communication technologies. In this paper, we will discuss the UWB pulse position multiple access modulation schemes using rake configurations with help of MATLAB simulations.

Keywords: UWB, PPM, PPM-TH, ISI.

I. Introduction

UWB transmission is a signal, that occupies a bandwidth of more than 25% of a center frequency, or more than 1.5GHz greater. The basic element in UWB radio technology is the use of Gaussian monocycle as shown in figure 1. in both time and frequency. [3][4].

Fig.1.UWB bandwidth in time & frequency domain

II. PPM Modulation

In PPM modulation, each pulse is delayed or sent in advance of a regular time scale. A binary communication system can be established with a forward or backward shift of the pulse in time. The data is encoded by adding an extra time shift “ δ_{shift} ” to the impulse as shown in Fig. The binary PPM signal is given by

$$s(t) = \sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} a_k p(t - kT_f \pm \delta_{shift}) \quad (1)$$

where the data modulation is done by small shifts in the pulse position δ_{shift} , $p(t)$ is the UWB pulse and T_f is the frame duration.